

1 **UBE2C is a switch that controls a conserved cancer cell proliferation program.**

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7 Cancer cells exploit multiple steps required for cell division to exert oncogenic force in order to promote
8 division of the cell. This includes the mitotic phase anaphase, where the sister chromatid is contacted at
9 the kinetochore for physical separation of the daughter DNA strand to the nascent cell. We discovered a
10 ubiquitin E2 enzyme, *UBE2C*, that functions as a downstream switch to control a conserved network of
11 cellular effectors functioning at the kinetochore including NUSAP1, TPX2, BUB1, CDK1, ASPM, MELK,
12 nucleotide synthesis machinery RRM2 and TK1, as well as the major solid tumor protein ECT2. Human
13 cancers differentially express and up-regulate UBE2C at a level that surpasses the vast majority of the
14 transcriptome, and depletion of UBE2C in cancer cells results in loss of the entirety of the aforementioned
15 program. The UBE2C tumor survival program included interactions with the cyclin dependent kinase
16 inhibitor *CDKN3* and the human baculoviral inhibitor of apoptosis (IAP) repeat-containing gene *BIRC5*,
17 also known as survivin. UBE2C is a human solid tumor therapeutic target.
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